

ISSN : 2278-5655

*Multidisciplinary Scholarly Research Association, India
Aarhat Journals and Aarhat Publications*

AMIERJ

AARHAT MULTIDISCIPLINARY INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH JOURNAL
Peer Reviewed Referred Journal

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

This is to certify that, Mr./Ms./Mrs./Dr.

Mrs. Reshmi Rekha Charah

*has contributed a paper as author/co-author to **Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

*ISSN-2278-5655, **Volume–XI, Issue–IV, July - Aug 2022, SJIF Impact Factor: 8.169***

**SCHEDULED CASTES AND SCHEDULED TRIBES IN UNDER GRADUATE LEVEL OF DIBRUGARH UNIVERSITY
IN ASSAM- A CASE STUDY IN JORHAT DISTRICT**

The Editor in chief and The Editorial Board appreciate the Intellectual Contribution of the author/co-author.

PRAMILA THOKALE

(Managing Editor)